

PLACE OF FINANCIAL-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN THE HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In the modern competitive environment, the success of each and every healthcare institution depends mainly on the effectiveness of its operations. The **objective** of the present work is based on in-depth analysis of financial indicators for the activity of the University Multi-profile Hospital for Active Treatment (UMHAT) „Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL“ to evaluate the effectiveness of financial management, outline the main problems and propose guidelines for hospital’s future development in market competitiveness and dynamic health requirements.

To achieve financial stability and competitiveness of the hospital we should improve activity effectiveness via cost optimization, maintenance of strict financial discipline, control of payments collectability and reasonable investments in offering health services with high profitability health technologies.

Keywords: financial-economic analysis, effectiveness, management, hospital.

Introduction

In the modern competitive environment that results from market economy, the success of each and every healthcare institution depends mainly on the effectiveness of its operations. The analysis of healthcare institutions’ financial position is main element of the effective management. It becomes instrumental for achieving competitive advantages and for the elaboration of strategies for short-term and long-term development.

The financial management and control of resources become even more important for ensuring of high quality of medical services, as well as for stability and sustainability of institutions themselves. At the same time, the diminishing government funding of health sector raises additional requirements towards hospitals so that these could effectively manage their finance, optimize costs and implement sustainable financial strategies.

The financial analysis provides the necessary information for risk assessment, making informed decisions and formulating strategic directions for the future development of hospitals and their tailoring to the changes of healthcare system [9]. In this specific case, we will examine the financial condition of the UMHAT „Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL“, which will allow us to identify key aspects for the sustainable development of the healthcare system in Bulgaria and to draw conclusions that will serve as the basis for future reforms in the sector.

UMHAT „Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL“ is among the most essential healthcare institutions in Bulgaria, with many years of experience and reputation in emergency and intensive medical care, as well as among the largest clinical bases for attending postgraduate qualification

and specialization of doctors in Bulgaria [5]. The hospital services high number of patients yet it plays an important role in training medical personnel and scientific operations in the country. The healthcare institution faces various challenges such as increasing costs for personnel, materials, new technologies and equipment. Additionally, the need of investments and infrastructure modernization requires careful financial control and strategic planning.

The financial position of UMHAT „Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL“ is essential for its functioning and development. In this context, the annual financial statements provide important information that could be used for evaluation of hospital’s economic effectiveness, management of its resources and its capability to satisfy patients’ needs.

The analysis of company’s financial position is essential for its successful management. It makes it possible to unveil problematic areas, optimize costs and consider new opportunities for development [4; 7].

The **objective** of the present work is based on in-depth analysis of financial indicators for the activity of the UMHAT „Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL“ to evaluate the effectiveness of financial management, outline the main problems and propose guidelines for hospital’s future development in market competitiveness and dynamic health requirements.

Materials and methods: The research is based on a combination of theoretical and practical methods, which include qualitative and quantitative approaches, as well as specific financial analysis tools, which will allow the main problems to be outlined. A statistical method was also used for quantitative analysis and processing of the financial and economic data provided by the hospital’s reports for the period 2013-2022, as well as comparative and graphical analysis.

Results and discussion

The analysis of financial position of healthcare institutions is among the main aspects of managerial operations in healthcare. It provides the necessary information about the health of institutions' financial structure related to rendering medical services. The analysis is essential in order to ensure that healthcare institutions are capable of performing their obligations and ensure quality treatment to patients. This process not only measures the financial position of particular healthcare institution, but also provides foundations for making important managerial decisions that could impact the sustainable development of the latter [6].

The notion of financial position of healthcare institution covers the comprehensive measurement of its capability to generate sufficient funds for funding its operational activity. It includes not only current costs, but investments that are to be made in medical equipment, infrastructure and personnel training. Financial position is interrelated with other important indicators such as financial autonomy and indebtedness, liquidity, profitability and effectiveness [2; 3].

The indicators of financial autonomy are quantitative features of the degree of enterprise's financial independence from the creditors, i.e. the degree of using raised capital.

Figure 1: Financial autonomy ratio

During the analysed period the coefficient of financial autonomy has values that approximate 0, which means that healthcare institution could hardly cover raised capital with its ownership. The relatively low

growth of financial autonomy demonstrates that the hospital keeps relying to great degree on external funding sources (loans and other liabilities). Its highest value in 2021 was 0.38 [1].

Figure 2: Indebtedness ratio

Coefficient of financial indebtedness shows what part of liabilities is collateralized with equity. In 2013 and in 2014 the coefficient of indebtedness is with very high

values which demonstrates deteriorated financial stability and autonomy of the company. It is noteworthy that in the following years the values of this coefficient drastically decreased and in 2022 it was 2.85 [1]. The

coefficient values demonstrate that per 1 BGN equity there are around 3.00 BGN of debts on the average. This is relatively high value which means the hospital is still strongly dependent on external funding sources.

Liquidity is prerequisite for company solvency. The liquidity indicators are quantitative features of organization's capability to pay its current debts with the available short-term assets.

If the liquidity coefficient is equal to or higher than 1, this means that with the available short-term assets the enterprise covers its current debts [10].

Figure 3: Total liquidity ratio

Figure 4: Rapid liquidity ratio

During the first half of the analyzed period the values of coefficients of total and rapid liquidity are below the minimum required levels. Slight increase was noted in 2019 and in 2022 the coefficients are higher than 1, which demonstrates that the company potential to satisfy its debts gradually increases yet there are still not sufficient liquid assets to cover its current debts [1].

We should note that low values of liquidity ratios are not desirable, because these suggest insolvency and bankruptcy as well as too high liquidity since it is source of opportunity costs and benefits.

Figure 5. Absolute liquidity ratio

The coefficient of absolute liquidity measures the degree to which cash could cover short-term debts. Its values are less than 1 throughout the analyzed period whereas slight increase was observed only in 2020, yet after that they decreased once again [1]. This demonstrates that the healthcare institution has no sufficient financial resource in order to cover rapidly its current debts and with the available rapidly liquid assets it could not cover the operations performed for its activity.

The cost efficiency ratio is calculated as the ratio of revenue to operating expenses of the company. For the activity to be effective, the coefficient should not be less than 0.98. The graph shows that during the first five months of the analyzed period, the values are slightly below the minimum required levels. Since 2018, cost efficiency has increased slightly and reached 1, which indicates that the efficiency of the company's work is improving. However, in 2022 there is a slight decrease again [1].

Figure 6. Cost efficiency ratio

The cost efficiency ratio is closely related to the profitability ratio. Throughout most of the considered period (except for 2018-2020) the healthcare institution

has achieved mainly losses, hence its profitability is negative [1].

Figure 7: Profitability based on costs

Figure 8. Profitability based on revenue

The profitability of the hospital is an important indicator that characterizes the financial result of its overall activities. It provides information about the company's ability to generate profit and cover its expenses. The data from the figures show that it not only didn't generate a profit, but also suffered a loss.

Conclusion

As a result of the elaborated analysis we arrive to the conclusion that at present the Hospital develops in unstable financial environment [1], some of the reasons for this are:

- the defined prices of clinical pathways do not provide full cover of the fixed costs and the ones necessary for patient treatment;
- nonpayment by the fund of the medical services rendered to the patients which exceed the volumes defined by the National Health Insurance Fund;
- funding for capital costs by the principal – Ministry of Health – is minimized;
- insufficient funding of emergency activity by the Ministry of Health etc.

UMHAT „Tsaritsa Yoanna – ISUL“ **demonstrates successful efforts in optimizing resources and adapting to changes of healthcare system.** The healthcare institution has all the opportunities for good organization of the diagnostic and treatment process, related to achievement of optimal qualitative indicators and good quality of medical activity; in order to expand the opportunities for lecturing and scientific activity. To achieve financial stability and competitiveness of the hospital we should improve activity effectiveness via cost optimization, maintenance of strict financial discipline, control of payments collectability and reasonable investments in offering health services with high profitability health technologies.

The place of financial-economic analysis in the hospital managerial process should be reviewed and evaluated not as search and use of the opportunities for current growth of financial revenues, but as achievement of strategic stability and competitiveness, via creation and maintenance of prerequisites for continuous quality improvement of diagnostic-treatment process and cares after the patient. This long-term objective is

achieved as a result of more effective use of resources for the production of hospital services [8].

In order to ensure sustainable development in the future, the Hospital should improve its results mainly via increase of operation revenues. Some opportunities to achieve this are:

- Investments in new technologies and equipment that would improve treatment effectiveness and decrease costs for medical procedures;
- Expansion of ambulatory services and decrease of hospitalization need, which could optimize costs and increase the hospital capacity to receive patients;
- Optimization of cost management for personnel and medical consumables via stricter control onto costs and identification of areas in which we could achieve cost effectiveness, etc.

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